

This is a **Version of Record** of the research article published by Wiley in the journal titled *Asian Politics & Policy*, 5 April 2023, pp. 205-225, Online ISSN: 1943-0787, available online at <https://doi.org/10.1111/aspp.12683>.

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This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe coordination and support action 101079069 — EUVIP — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03.

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Enabling activist resilience: Bystander protection during protest crackdowns in Myanmar

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Funding information

Cornell University; European Union, Grant/Award Number: No101079069

Abstract

What accounts for the survival and long-term participation of activists in contentious movements under repression? I argue for the role of an important yet oft-neglected factor: protective support by civilian bystanders. I propose that, mainly motivated by victim-oriented sympathy, bystanders engage in high-risk protection that helps activists to escape crackdowns and bolsters their dedication to the movement. To test my theoretical claims, I examine hard cases for activist survival at the height of state violence during military rule in Myanmar between 1988 and 2010, with an original qualitative data set consisting of oral history interviews and written accounts by more than 100 protest observers and former pro-democracy activists. The data set presents an unprecedented number of voices from the average, non-contentious general public, which are mostly missing in existing research on social movements. This approach generates a fresh perspective to better understand opportunities and constraints around movement entrepreneurs in hostile environments.

KEYWORDS

activist resilience, authoritarian repression, military rule, Myanmar, protest movement

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INTRODUCTION

Studies of popular contentious movements have shown that grassroots activists' survival and steadfast dedication contribute to movement resilience, because they either pass down their practical knowledge and ideological inspiration to new movement leaders and participants or directly coordinate subsequent protests (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011; Sawyers & Meyer, 1999; Taylor, 1989; Whittier, 2018). However, authoritarian regimes with zero-tolerance policies toward the opposition are hostile environments for dissidents to persevere. While most studies of contentious politics under authoritarian control have highlighted activists' strategies to avoid drawing attention from the authorities (Fu, 2018; O'Brien & Li, 2006; O'Brien & Stern, 2008), few have analyzed how they managed to stay resilient against direct state violence, that is, to survive and continue igniting further cycles of mobilization.

To address this gap in the literature, my study presents a novel framework that incorporates an important yet under-analyzed player into the interaction between a state and its challengers: civilian bystanders and observers of opposition activism. I argue that, in hard-lined repressive regimes, although the majority of the general public might not engage in high-risk activism, many of them still play a politically meaningful role by performing high-risk rescue toward protesters under crackdown, who they consider to be innocent victims. Abundant examples from recent protest events, including in Myanmar after the 2021 military coup, have shown people defying violent risks in informing and advising protesters on how to stay safe, forming protective barriers around protesters, taking injured protesters to the hospital, giving them medical treatments, or hiding dissidents from the authorities (D. Blum, 2020; Myanmar Now, 2021; Nu Nu Lusan et al., 2021). I hypothesize that this contributes to keeping dissidents alive and dedicated to contentious movements. To examine my theoretical claims, I analyze an original qualitative data set on the Burmese pro-democracy movement during 1988–2010, consisting of oral history interviews and written accounts by Myanmar residents from diverse demographic and political backgrounds.

My findings make an important contribution to the field of Burma studies. The long-term resilience of the Burmese urban pro-democracy movement is one of the most impressive yet under-explained among all cases of collective activism under authoritarianism. Indeed, the five decades of military dictatorship in Myanmar were a period of brutal repression against pro-democracy activism. Ever since General Ne Win took over the state in 1962 until General Than Shwe ceded power to a quasi-civilian government in 2011, anti-regime urban protests sprang up continuously yet were cracked down upon heavily. In every decade during the 50 years of military strongman rule, in the city of Yangon alone, there are numerous records of strikes and demonstrations by students, workers, monks, and the general public that the sitting junta crushed (Boudreau, 2004; Fink, 2013; Htun Aung Gyaw, 1997; Kyaw Yin Hlaing, 2009; Lintner, 1989).

Nonetheless, in the face of constant suppression, large-scale urban pro-democracy protests still re-emerged with the same spirit and fervor through the years. A variety of mobilization resources lived on, in the form of either key personnel, knowledge, experiences, or revolutionary spirit that rekindled fresh rounds of antigovernment demonstrations throughout the decades. Activists who escaped repression worked with new generations of activists, adapted their strategies, and launched further contentious cycles with the hope that their new attempts would be more effective in generating pressure at home and abroad for regime change. Yet, while many studies have discussed at length the trials and survival of the Burmese pro-democracy activists, they do not present causal mechanisms for how the activists survived

or perished at the height of state attacks (Beatty, 2011; Fink, 2009; Kyaw Yin Hlaing 2007; Lintner, 1989). My research fills this gap by highlighting a key factor that shapes dissident survival in dictatorial Myanmar.

More importantly, my theoretical framework has broader implications for understanding protest dynamics in hostile environments across the globe. We can find repressive patterns similar to the Burmese military juntas' in modern-day autocracies, such as the Communist party-states; post-Soviet dictatorships; monarchies in the Gulf region; military regimes in the Middle East and North Africa; and dominant-party regimes in Sub-Saharan Africa. As these regimes are highly intolerant toward politically contentious mobilizations, protesters there are also expected to encounter a weakly politicized public audience as well as state-sanctioned lethal attacks and arrests that aim to silence and decimate dissent. Hence, protection by ordinary bystanders and observers during government crackdowns should play an equally substantial role in sustaining activist resilience in those cases as in the Myanmar case.

In the following sections, I first outline theoretical and empirical gaps in the social movement literature and then present my theoretical framework. The paper subsequently introduces original qualitative data from the Burmese urban pro-democracy movement that I analyze to examine my claims. Finally, I conclude by highlighting my study's contributions and suggesting future research directions.

CURRENT LITERATURE ON ACTIVISM UNDER REPRESSION

Participants of contentious campaigns under repressive regimes face high risk of state surveillance, infiltration, harassment, arrest, and targeted killings. Existing literature has mainly outlined how these activists might evade the state's attention, either by engaging in atomized or small-scale resistance (Fu, 2018; O'Brien & Li, 2006) or associating themselves with existing non-contentious institutions (O'Brien & Stern, 2008). However, few have analyzed in-depth how they might survive government crackdowns during mass protest events to continue their activism. Relevant works have either highlighted adaptations in mobilization strategies or individual activists' own updating of self-defense strategies.

First, to minimize the risks of state infiltration and bolster the effectiveness of mutual support during crackdowns, activists mostly built mobilizing networks through familial bonds and long-term friendships. For instance, comparing student activism under different levels of authoritarianism in 1989 China and 1990 Taiwan, Wright (2008) demonstrated how friendship becomes the only viable basis for maintaining trust and building resilient networks among dissidents in more repressive environments (p. 50). Similarly, explaining variation in sustained human rights activism under military juntas in Latin America, Loveman (1998) found that existing social bonds—particularly Catholic church networks—provided a high level of trust and extensive foundation for resilient activism. In the case of Myanmar, the peer networks of students and monks across the country were the breeding grounds for mobilizing and launching protests nationwide (Boudreau, 2004; Kyaw Yin Hlaing, 2008).

Furthermore, by scrutinizing the years of hiding and planning resistance by Burmese dissidents inside the country, Fink (2013) and Beatty (2011) demonstrated how a large number of activists were able to continue their work and escape arrests thanks to unwavering protection by familial networks. As Beatty (2011) found, activist families served as critical channels for information transfer and networking, effective cover for political meetings, and

important source of financial support. Discreet help from friendly neighbors who warned activists “in advance about house searches” or sabotaged these searches also plays a significant role in Fink’s (2013) account of dissidents’ resilience (Location No. 3101). However, at the height of mass crackdowns during protest events, activists are less likely to be able to call for support from home or trusted friends and more likely to be among strangers or in unfamiliar neighborhoods. In such cases, there lacks rigorous empirical evidence for the effectiveness of personal networks in helping dissidents escape security forces’ high-intensity repression.

Second, regarding resource mobilization, existing works have described how activist groups might prepare themselves in advance against crackdowns by mobilizing collective capacity for protest safety. For instance, during Hong Kong’s two disruptive pro-democracy protests, the 2014 Umbrella Movement and 2019–2020 Anti-ELAB Movement, recent literature highlighted collective attempts to build safe zones for protesters (Li & Tong, 2020) and gather donations for safety equipment as well as “medical treatment, psychological counseling and legal advice” (Cheng et al., 2022). Nonetheless, these studies have yet to theorize or empirically test the effect of such strategies on the activists’ survival or long-term participation.

Last but not least, other works emphasized individual activists’ own updating of their capacity for self-defense, especially by learning from others’ experiences. Recent analyses on Asia’s pro-democracy Milk Tea Alliance have demonstrated how protesters from Myanmar and Thailand, via online platforms, adopted Hong Kong protesters’ strategies to deceive the authorities about protest locations (Sombatpoonsiri, 2021) and equip themselves with protective gears (Reuters Staff, 2021). However, there still lacks rigorous examination of how protesters’ learning of safety tactics affects their chances of survival. As other works on protest crackdowns in the Arab region and Latin America have demonstrated, autocrats also learn from their peers to update their own response strategies and have different predilections for repression (Heydemann & Leenders, 2014; Olar, 2019). Hence, a successful self-defense tactic in one political environment might become ineffective or even counter-productive in another.

Indeed, activist resilience might depend instead on rescue by strangers in their immediate proximity, that is, ordinary bystanders and observers. In the next section, I present my theory of activist resilience as a result of bystander protection amid state violence.

THEORY OF BYSTANDER PROTECTION AND ACTIVIST RESILIENCE

Since protest campaigns are openly contentious acts that aim to induce reactions from the general public, bystander response—in all of its diverse forms—is a highly relevant variable. I define bystanders as those who do not take part in the political agenda of either the state or challengers. Only by taking into account the various types of bystander reactions toward contentious actors can we construct a full landscape of political opportunity structure (POS) that surrounds contentious mobilization in a dictatorship.

The social movement literature conceptualizes POS as external opportunities or threat to contentious actors that are generally shaped by regime structure. According to Tarrow (2011), while opportunities include “(1) opening of access to participation for new actors, (2) evidence of realignment within the polity, (3) availability of influential allies, and (4) emerging splits within the leaders”; threat refers to “the states’ and other actors’ capacity or will to control dissent” (pp. 164–165). My research problematizes the top-down, one-dimensional approach of conceptualizing threat. As interactions between the state and challengers do not occur in a

vacuum, but in populated towns and cities, effective suppression of contentious mobilization does not depend solely on a state's own capacity, but also on actions by an oft-neglected third force: a large population of bystanders.

Citizens under a repressive regime might hold grievances toward their political system and refuse to dedicate to the regime agenda, however, existing studies show that they rarely openly challenge the regime either, largely due to perception of high risks (of state violence, arrest, or harassment) or low efficacy (of resisting a unified entity with a much less coordinated force) (O'Brien & Stern, 2008; Rodan, 2013; Scott, 1985; Sika, 2012; Tarrow, 2011). Hence, during public contentious events such as mass protests, the majority of the general public tend to display withdrawal, that is, not concerned about or adhered to the agenda of either the state or challengers.

So what role might ordinary bystanders play in the dynamics and outcomes of contentious politics? I argue that although they are not motivated to openly oppose the authorities, a large number of civilians engage in high-risk protection toward protesters as they perceive the protesters as victims of unjustified state violence and sympathize with them. To invoke such sympathy, many movements actively broadcast images of vulnerable protesters as benign members of the public who suffer brutal police attacks and shootings (Aytaç et al., 2018; Pearlman, 2017). According to the literature on rescue of victims of mass killing, such images might lead to bystander sympathy that motivates protective support (Pagano & Huo, 2007; L. A. Blum, 1992; Saab et al., 2015; Thomas et al., 2009). As Thomas et al. (2009) find, “[sympathy]’s key motivating action tendency is to attempt to help the disadvantaged and mitigate their suffering” (p. 318). For instance, in studying how emotions motivate responses among U.S. citizens towards Iraqi citizens—“victims” of the 2003 War, Pagano and Huo (2007) find that sympathy correlates with support for humanitarian action to improve the welfare of people in Iraq. Hence, while unwilling to participate in protests, bystanders’ active protection of protesters under crackdown demonstrates the capacity of victim-oriented sympathy in motivating high-risk, politically meaningful actions.

More importantly, I propose that *bystander protection diminishes the efficiency of repression and boosts activists’ morale, and therefore, determines not only how many protesters survive but also to which extent surviving protesters continue their participation*. First, by diminishing security forces’ repressive capacity and enabling protesters’ escape, various forms of bystander protection increase dissidents’ survival chance. Acts such as blocking security forces’ access to protesters with barricades and human chains or engaging in backlash attacks against state security directly moderate a regime’s ability to crackdown. Moreover, by informing activists about imminent crackdown, providing them with shelter and material support, assisting their escape plans, or treating their injuries, sympathetic bystanders also help to ensure protesters’ secure exit. I illustrate the hypothesized effects in Figure 1 below and will examine each of them in the empirical analysis.

Secondly, I propose that bystander protection increases the likelihood of activists’ continued participation in popular movements. Findings from the literature on high-risk activism (Pearlman, 2018; Wood, 2003) suggest that activist commitment depends on their (1) sense of validation for their work and (2) perception of risk in re-engaging in activism. I theorize that being rescued by the public would affect both aspects. First, bystander protection lowers activists’ risk perception while they engage in future protests, since they can rely on an extra source of support during state repression. Second, bystander protective support is an important stamp of validation that fosters activists’ attachment to their work, not out of the protest’ political efficacy but out of its meaning toward the public. Activists are likely to consider

FIGURE 1 Effects of bystander protection.

FIGURE 2 Theory of bystander protection.

civilian protection as not only a manifestation of the public's altruistic sympathy toward individual protesters but also approval of the movement as well as desire for the movement to continue. I expect this to provide an additional sense of purpose and moral obligation that inspires activists to remain active and dedicated to their popular movement, despite its difficulties.

I synthesize my overarching theoretical framework in Figure 2.

QUALITATIVE DATA AND METHODS

Data from Myanmar

I test my theoretical arguments against an original qualitative data set on the Burmese pro-democracy movement during 1988–2010. Between late 2017 and early 2018, I conducted semistructured oral history interviews and collected written accounts by more than 100 Myanmar residents from diverse demographic backgrounds, who witnessed or were involved in two major protest events in 1988 and 2007 (see Figure A in Appendix). Despite having these two events as entry points for data collection, I probed and searched for people's protest-related activities and observations throughout 1988–2010. Moreover, although mainly Yangon city-based, my sample extended to cities and towns in different parts of Myanmar, including Hmawbi (Yangon Region), Mandalay (Mandalay Region), Magwe (Magwe Region), Mawla-myne (Mon State), Myitkyina (Kachin State), and Tedim (Chin State). Hence, this data set provides a large number of voices from the ordinary, non-contentious general public from a

wide range of socioeconomic backgrounds, which are mostly missing in existing research on social movements in dictatorships.

To build trust with interviewees while maximizing the diversity of the sample, I worked with private schools, libraries, and institutions in Yangon and their affiliates to recruit respondents. I interviewed 69 residents (including 43 bystanders) about 1988 events and 44 residents (including 32 bystanders) about 2007. I then supplement the interview data with written accounts from 24 published autobiographies, memoirs, and interviews by non-activists and former activists. The data collection process stopped once my sample reached all of the sampling criteria (regarding geographical, demographic, and political representations) and the data reached saturation, that is, when new data offered too little new information (Bertaux, 1981; Creswell, 2014; Weiss, 1994).

By collaborating with local organizations, the research protocol aligns with local social standards and expectations. Myanmar's political liberalization during 2012–2020 was also conducive to my interviews and archival work. Many former politicians and student activists in Myanmar had already provided interviews to newspapers, magazines, and television shows and authored memoirs that were publicly distributed throughout the country. They openly discussed their historical antigovernment activities and state repression under the military regimes, without having faced any threats or repercussions. As there is little censorship surrounding the 1988 and 2007 events during my fieldwork period, the probability of interviewees misrepresenting their own experiences is diminished.

To further maximize the accuracy of my respondents' answers, I followed recommended practices in oral history. Oral historians have long studied and recognized the risks of memory loss or incorrect recall as memory stories can be affected by popular narratives in interviewees' surroundings. Nonetheless, according to Bosi and Reiter (2014), oral history is still a widely used method in social movement studies as it offers a significant advantage in uncovering “subjugated voices, excluded from the historic records for reasons of political, geographic, class, gender, or ethnic affiliation” (p. 130).

First, to provide adequate time for the respondents to recollect and potentially resolve any contradicting memories, I thoroughly explained the research topic to them at least one day in advance during the recruitment process. Then, during each interview, to stimulate a respondent's memory, I started by asking them about the surrounding contexts when they witnessed the protest events as well as their age, location, and occupation at the time. Furthermore, without pressing the respondents to discuss their engagement in any particular actions, I let them freely share their most significant memories of the protest events first before following up on more specific details on their attitudes, feelings, and reactions. After each interview, I assessed the logical development of their story and contacted them if further clarification was necessary.

According to Thomson (2011), significant events that “have had a dramatic impact or been subject to physical sensations or powerful emotion” tend to become consolidated in long-term memory (p. 85). Despite occurring one to three decades ago, my respondents' experiences in 1988 and 2007 came across as such memorable events since these urban residents could describe in vivid details not only the unprecedented events that had taken place but also their extreme feelings and emotions at the time—either fear, anger, paranoia, joy, or pride. To further ensure the reliability of my data, I verified the events in the respondents' stories against other sources of published information, mainly reports by international human rights organizations (Amnesty International, 1990, 1992, 1993, 1996, 1997, 2004a, 2004b, 2005; Human Rights Watch, 2007, 2009; and Special Rapporteur of the Commission on Human

Rights, 1993–2007) and publications by recognized experts (Beatty, 2011; Boudreau, 2004; Fink, 2009, 2013; Htun Aung Gyaw, 1997; Kyaw Yin Hlaing, 2007, 2008; Lintner, 1989; Mya Maung, 1992). Hence, except for the respondents' personal attitudes and emotions, only observable incidents that are also reported in the above sources become part of my empirical analysis. They include occurrences during the protest events, government crackdowns, bystanders' behavioral reactions, and activists' withdrawal or continued participation in the movement.

Finally, to distinguish bystander protection from protest participation, I observe the respondents' *motivations* via their attitudes and emotions. Certain acts might appear as both, for example, forming human chains around protesters or giving food and medicine to protesters. However, whether an action constitutes bystander protection or protest participation depends *not* on its form but on whether the individual is *only* motivated to help suffering victims or *also* to oppose the repressive regime. I consider a respondent's act as bystander protection if she simultaneously expresses fear or uninterest in protest participation yet willingness to rescue protesters under crackdown. On the other hand, if a respondent displays pride and excitement in being part of a protest, I count her actions as protest participation.

Hard cases for activist resilience: pro-democracy protests in 1988 and 2007

This section highlights the difficult conditions for activist resilience during two periods of devastating repression that crippled the Burmese pro-democracy movement's leadership: the final days of Four-eight Uprising (1988) and Saffron Revolution (2007).

In 1988, the country witnessed the “Four-eight” or “8888” Uprising on August 8, a culmination of student activism in Yangon due to the students' grievances at General Ne Win's one-party dictatorship, including its sudden demonetization of the national currency *Myanmar kyat* in 1987 and police brutality against student protesters in March and June 1988. Starting in late July, student activists broadcast a call for a Four-eight nationwide uprising against the Burmese Socialist Programme Party regime. The main demands were to have the current government step down and to establish a democratic regime in Burma (Myanmar's official English name at the time). The Four-eight Uprising was at its pinnacle in late August.

Then, on September 18, General Saw Maung publicly announced a military coup. The government subsequently set up night curfew and banned gatherings of five or more people. Soldiers and military trucks started patrolling across all townships and were ready to fire at anyone caught in the streets. Hence, the protesters who defied the order received heavy crackdown and suffered a large number of casualties. Thousands of activists then fled to the border areas or abroad. This marked the end of Four-eight.¹

Nonetheless, various urban pro-democracy protests sprang up during the 1990s–2000s, including the large-scale Saffron Revolution in September 2007, despite an extremely hostile political environment. The immediate trigger for mobilization in 2007 was General Than Shwe government's sudden reduction in fuel subsidy in mid-August, which led to a significant increase in fuel prices. Monks started to take to the streets since they sympathized with their supporters' economic plight. But the main event that ignited nationwide protests was the military's attacks against the protesting monks in Pakkoku that left many of them severely injured.

Starting on September 17, monks staged protest marches all over the country. A week later, starting on September 26, Than Shwe's government announced to take actions against the protesters and banned gathering of five or more people. The security forces, comprising of soldiers, riot police, and hired thugs, began to violently crack down on demonstrators, beating, shooting, and arresting anyone in or near protest sites in broad daylight. State security also violently raided multiple monasteries at night, attacking and arresting their resident monks. Thus, the Revolution officially ended by the end of September. In its aftermath, the number of political prisoners significantly increased to more than 2000 (Special Rapporteur of the Commission on Human Rights, 2007, p. 13).

Indeed, on the final days of both Four-eight and Saffron, once the order to crack down was issued, state repression became systematic and widespread. No protest units were spared and movement leadership was damaged. Hence, these are hard cases for activist resilience. In the next section, I will discuss my findings on the mechanisms through which protective acts by ordinary bystanders emerged and played a significant role in keeping grassroots activists alive and dedicated despite government attacks.

FINDINGS

Variation in bystander responses

My data show that the majority of bystanders who witnessed either the Four-eight Uprising or Saffron Revolution were reluctant to face the risks of opposing the regime and hence not motivated to participate in political activism. According to personal accounts by ordinary Yangon residents, the actual turnout at the beginning of 1988 Four-eight Uprising and during 2007 Saffron Revolution was restricted to the leading activists—either students or monks—and their core supporters. Although most people did not hide their grievances and contempt at the Ne Win or Than Shwe government, they chose to stay on the sidelines instead.

One interviewee shares his thought process in 1988: “I was interested in participating but I was a government staff at the time. So I just guarded my ward but I didn't go to any strikes” (Interview 101). Even a former student activist in 2007 concurs: “I had been so excited before to join [the protesting monks], and then there were some students who got afraid. [...] The government had intelligence personnel with local wear, not uniform. They were everywhere at that time. If they saw us, it would not be good for our education. So we decided not to be involved” (Interview 100). Thus, the perceived risks in joining political protests, such as getting arrested, getting fired (from government jobs), or getting expelled from school prevented most bystanders from demonstrating. Instead, most people were more inclined to engage in other non-overt acts that have been neglected in the social movement literature, including sympathetic protection.

Indeed, perceiving movement organizers and participants as benign members of the public, who posed little threat toward the surrounding neighborhoods was key in encouraging bystanders to watch and tolerate protesters. For instance, one organizer of the 2007 protests recalls the appealing visual effect that the marches achieved since the first day: “It was a very beautiful scene. [The monks] did not chant any anti-government slogans. They just chanted *Metta Sutta*² and marched” (Interview 26). A local resident also describes public tolerance of the movement as a result of this strategy: “As it was led by the Buddhist monks and the monks peacefully chanted *Metta Sutta*, everybody was interested and went to help by themselves.

People came out voluntarily because they liked the movement led by the monks chanting *Metta Sutta* for a good cause” (Interview 91). In addition, my interviewees recount how, in both 1988 and 2007, most demonstrations marched in an organized and friendly manner across different neighborhoods to gain public tolerance and approval.

On the other hand, bystanders' perception of protesters as causing danger toward their communities precluded bystander interest or support. For instance, many members of minority ethnic communities regarded Bamar people, the majority ethnic group that also controlled the military and government, as their oppressors for decades. As Bamar Buddhists were thought to make up the vast majority of urban pro-democracy protesters, there were cases where this existing ethnic tension hindered non-Bamar from supporting protesters. A Karen man, who is an ethnic minority living in Yangon in 2007, recalls how his Karen neighborhood was not bothered much by state repression of ethnic Bamar monks and protesters: “Most people in our community are Karen people, they didn't really care. Most of the people who were suffering were Bamar people so it had nothing to do with us” (Interview 15).

Another example comes from a politically knowledgeable Muslim religious leader in Yangon. Even though he noticed the non-violent march by the monks in 2007, he did not support them at first because he was aware of a previous state-sponsored sectarian unrest between Muslim and Buddhist communities, which made him suspect that these monks had malicious intent. Living downtown, his perception only changed after constant exposure to the monks' selfless acts:

Before 2007, some religious violence against Muslims happened in upper Myanmar, like Kyaukse. Some mosques were attacked and crushed. So I was a little bit worried, not knowing whether these monks were good monks or bad monks. That's why I didn't trust them and just observed. But later on I realized these monks were good monks. Because it was raining for 3-4 days, and these monks were not asked to do this, they volunteered. I witnessed their hardship and sympathized with them. (Interview 92)

Hence, only after witnessing their orderly marches under heavy rain while chanting well-wishes for everyone was he convinced that the monks were harmless, which motivated him to let the Saffron protesters take refuge at his home when the security forces started shooting at them.

Moreover, since the general public had access and frequently paid attention to foreign radio and TV channels, the broadcasting of images and stories of brutal repression against protesters also played a significant role in invoking victim-oriented sympathy. In 2007, many Yangon residents remember how, as soon as government crackdowns commenced, they and their neighbors cried when they saw images of monks demonstrating for hours under heavy rain and getting beaten by the security forces. As stated by one observer: “This government was destroying Buddhism, they did not care at all about the monks. So that was why the people like us came along and locked arms to protect the monks” (Interview 25). Similarly, another interviewee details the immediate effect of her exposure to news of state violence against high school and university students at the beginning of Four-eight on her subsequent participation in sympathetic rallies in solidarity with the victims: “The BBC Burmese service motivated people by announcing about students being killed on the streets. They were at the age of high school and university students. Because we got the information, all university students from around there came out” (Interview 99). Hence, the framing of protesters as innocent civilians was necessary to evoke bystanders' sympathy and motivate them to rescue later on when protesters faced mass brutality.

People became ready to help, shelter, or hide protesters at the height of state repression.³ Most of my interviewees did not even mention risks when they discussed the dangerous circumstances when they offered protective support. For instance, in 1988, many bystanders rushed to send injured protesters to the hospital after government crackdowns. One bystander recalls: “At Their Phyu, the soldiers were blocking the road with cars and aiming the guns at the crowd of protesters and public speakers. Later, I saw that a student was shot and I sent him to the clinic” (Interview 101). Others directly attacked the riot police to force them to stop injuring protesters. A student activist in 1988 describes: “We were blocked by police force when we reached near Myae Ni Gone township. When students tried to go through the police, they were beaten and arrested. When the people from the quarter saw that sight that students were injured brutally by the police, they came out and threw rocks at the police. So, the police were injured too” (Interview 3).

Similarly, in 2007, many local residents also formed security lines, more popularly known as “human chains,” on both sides of the protesting monks as people came to regard this action as protecting the “good” monks from government crackdowns. One protest leader remembers: “On September 26 and 27, after the soldiers shot the monks, the people were not afraid anymore. Because they were very angry and shocked: they even shot the monks—the first class of the country. So people and students followed the demonstration” (Interview 26). Many interviewees were impressed at the discipline and determination of the security lines in defending the monks against state violence. A university student in Yangon who passed by multiple townships in 2007 recalls: “I saw that near Hledan, the police tried to ask the march to stop but the people did not stop. The police wanted to get into the monks’ rows and to open the hand clasps but the people stood still and the police could not break them up” (Interview 119).

Moreover, a resident of South Okkalapa township in 2007 who was part of a human chain emphasized people’s unity to ensure the monks’ safety: “The monks from the Kyaikkasan monastery went out to protest. From my neighborhood, we, young and old people gathered and surrounded the monks. We held hands. When the shooting happened, in one area, the police were waiting with three or four cars and they said: ‘If you get into this area, we will arrest everyone.’ But from our side, monks and people kept marching and shouting” (Interview 19). Many people also came to the monks’ rescue during the peak of military raiding of monasteries: “At a monastery in South Okkalapa, when things happened there, my neighbors went to watch. I saw the police forces surrounding the monastery and people came to see and fight them back, throwing rocks” (Interview 19). Hence, these actions exemplify high-risk collective protection during the Saffron event.

As the evidence from both the 1988 and 2007 events corroborate, the public’s sympathy toward victims of unjust suffering was crucial in motivating Yangon residents’ protection of protesters during the governments’ heavy crackdowns. In the next section, I elaborate on the effect of various forms of bystander protection toward both activist survival and long-term participation in the urban pro-democracy movement.

Effect of bystander protection

Activist survival

Activists were more likely to escape repression if they received bystander protection during these very high-risk situations. I illustrate in Figure 3 a timeline of protective support before, during, and after mass crackdowns that directly affected protesters’ fate.

FIGURE 3 Timeline of bystander protection at the height of government crackdown.

First, before the mass crackdowns began, an important form of bystander protection that helped protesters to avoid repression and arrests was local residents informing the protesters of government threats and troop movements so that they could go into hiding in advance. A protester in 1988 recounts his experience: “When the government announced the military coup, I did not know about it because I was participating in the march. So after the march was dismissed, when I was on my way back, I saw a sign written with chalk near downtown that said: ‘There was a coup announcement in the afternoon, so go back home.’ Some ordinary residents were worried that after curfew, all the people on the streets would be shot or killed by the soldiers. So they made the signs to inform the demonstrators” (Interview 24). Many activists were also informed by their sympathetic neighbors to flee when the military came looking for them as well.

Another form of collective protection in terms of barricades or human chains against attacks of the security forces was also crucial in shielding a large number of dissidents from state repression. A resident of Thingangyun township in 1988 recalls: “Military troops from other towns wanted to enter Yangon to help the troops here repress the protesters. We knew that if the troops get to downtown, they would make the children and protesters suffer. So our neighbors cut down coconut trees to block the military cars” (Interview 130). A former NLD activist in Bogalay city expresses his gratefulness for the human shields that separated the movement speakers from state-hired thugs: “On September 5th, thirteen people demonstrated. Then, I encouraged people in the city to participate and surround the thirteen speakers to protect them from Swan Arr Shin. So they were able to give public speeches” (Interview 147). Thus, such protection allowed the Saffron movement to persist in his town.

In addition, backlash attacks against violent security forces and shelters for runaway activists helped a large number of dissidents to escape arrests in the midst of repression. A former student activist in 1988 attests to this: “When the people from this quarter saw that students were brutally injured by the police, they came out and threw rocks at the police. So, the police were injured too. [...] As a result, we were able to separate from our colleagues and hide in safe places. I was not arrested” (Interview 3). Protesters were also able to avoid arrests by taking shelters at sympathetic bystanders’ houses and monasteries: “The security forces were looking for me. So I had to take refuge at people’s houses and sometimes had to stay all night in the restroom.” (Interview 132); “After the military took over, the student activists could not go

back home. Here, the Maggin monastery is very famous for hiding the activists” (Interview 108).

Furthermore, these secret shelters helped movement members to continue staging protests without being caught by the security forces. A South Okkalapa resident describes: “When the protesters saw the police car, the march dispersed. They went into the neighborhood to hide. Then, when the military cars were gone, they gathered again and continued demonstrating” (Interview 103). Another protester details how sympathetic bystanders downtown helped him to evade the military in multiple ways: “I was protesting near a market on Maha Bandula street. Then, four military cars arrived and soldiers came out. People from inside the market yelled ‘Go inside this market!’ so everyone ran in there. Then we opened the back door of the market and escaped to another street. At that time, people on that street told us not to move together but break up into small groups of two or three people. Later, we were able to reconvene at another site to protest again” (Interview 106).

However, not all protesters were able to escape crackdown. For the dissidents who were injured, medical rescue was critical to their survival. According to Naung Kyaw’s (2013) account, right after the initial bouts of repression in 1988, there were much fewer people protesting on the streets. Instead, the Rangoon General Hospital (RGH) was full of injured protesters and many local residents came to volunteer and donate blood, medicine, and food. When members of the public came to volunteer, the hospital staff assigned them with specific responsibilities so that medical treatments would be efficient. A resident who lived near RGH in 1988 recalls his important duty as a medical volunteer after the bloody coup September 18 occurred: “I volunteered at the Rangoon Hospital at Lanmadaw township. At the time, many people were shot by the military during the military coup. [...] After the shooting, the injured people had to be taken with ambulances to the Rangoon Hospital. At the time, there was no fuel for the ambulances, so I had to go around and asked for fuel. People donated a lot” (Interview 116). Many opposition members were only able to survive and rejoin the movement after receiving operations at the Rangoon General Hospital, as a large number of accounts from my interview and archival data confirm.

Besides rescue by RGH teams, a student activist recalls the role of other sympathetic supporters in providing temporary treatment during Four-eight: “The military used teargas to disperse us so we had to run into the nearby neighborhoods. The smoke was so terrible that we could not stand it. The local residents there saw this and became very upset as well. So they gave us water” (Interview 137). Overall, thanks to timely assistance by medical professionals and local residents, many activists were able to get treated and carry out further protests.

Finally, civilians’ discreet assistance in various forms was crucial for the success of activists’ escape plan from urban centers. For instance, during Saffron, according to a memoir by monk protest leader Ashin Htavara (2015), when he was hiding from the government and sleeping at train stations to avoid the military raids of monasteries, concerned residents who heard about the raids gave him food and took care of him. The monk activist was also able to flee Yangon after the government crackdown of Saffron thanks to a local resident who generously sheltered him and gave him civilian clothes to disguise himself, and a sympathetic taxi driver who took personal risk to help him to get out of the city (Ashin Htavara, 2015). Another former student activist in 1988 remembers very clearly how he could not have fled from the government’s manhunt without strangers’ help: “That very evening, I had to leave Yangon. There were many security checkpoints. I did not feel safe so I used a handkerchief to cover my mouth. When I reached the checkpoint, a group of female students approached me and said: ‘We know you are a student leader, give your bag to us. Women’s bags are not thoroughly searched.’ So they

helped me carry my bag” (Interview 7). Hence, bystanders’ high-risk protection was critical toward activist survival.

In the next section, I will demonstrate how these actions are also important determinants of activists’ long-term participation in the pro-democracy movement.

Activists’ long-term dedication

First, bystander protection has an indirect, positive effect on activists’ continued participation by helping them to avoid risks of violence or imprisonment. For opposition members who escaped arrests thanks to the help of sympathetic civilians, the lack of punitive experiences in prison made them become more risk-acceptant and willing to take leadership roles to organize future protests. A former student activist in 1988 recalls: “NLD stood as an opposition party and ABFSU as a student organization to overthrow the military regime. After these leaders were arrested and put in prison, we carried on the organizations’ task. We led the second line” (Interview 11). Another dissident shares the same determination: “The military intelligence from the dictatorship arrested the student leaders and imprisoned all of them. However, students that remained outside, with their small resources, continued to gather young people. We gathered the next generation to rebel” (Interview 2).

Indeed, many surviving activists carried on the momentum of the pro-democracy movement throughout the 1990s and 2000s. For instance, according to Ko Maki, a veteran activist who started his political career during Four-eight, since most people with interest in politics were already jailed in the 1990s, there was little movement on school campuses across the country. However, the remaining Four-eight student activists outside tried to connect with one another (Ko Maki, 2016). In 1991, Four-eight student activists led the 10D Movement on the campus of Yangon University at the occasion of Aung San Suu Kyi being awarded the Nobel Peace Prize.

Then, Four-eight activists again were involved in staging further student protests in 1996 and 1998. For instance, Ko Maki and his friends formed the Democratic Association of Youth and Student in 1992 to launch pro-democracy protests within school campuses. He went to university in 1995 and promoted the movement among fellow students in his first year, which created the foundation for the student movement in 1996 (Ko Maki, 2016). In addition, according to 88 Generation Student Pyone Cho’s (2013) account, his brother, Thet Win Aung, also a protest organizer in 1988, continued the movement after Pyone Cho and other students were arrested in 1989–early 1990s. Thet Win Aung, who fled the country after Four-eight and sneaked back into Yangon during mid-1990s, played a central role in helping to organize the student demonstrations in both 1996 and 1998.

Later on, at the launch of Saffron, former protest organizers from Four-eight and the 1990s student demonstrations worked closely with new activist leaders to prepare for a mass public campaign. A veteran activist who had organized protests in 1996, 1998, and 1999 recalls: “Since I already had some experience and knew about the Four-eight Uprising while Ko Sithu Maung and Ko Kyaw Ko Ko [ABFSU leaders during Saffron] were young people, I mainly helped to control and guide them” (Interview 19). Then, after government crackdowns, surviving Saffron activists founded Generation Wave, a pro-democracy youth movement, which creatively used music, pamphlets, car stickers, and graffiti to distribute anti-regime messages and urge people to continue fighting for political freedoms (Htein Lin, 2010, p. 145).

On the other hand, arrests and imprisonments not only shrank the number of movement members but also discouraged many former political prisoners from openly or actively organizing

demonstrations since they knew the brutality of the prison system first-hand. For example, a former political prisoner and NLD activist became much more risk-averse and avoided directly participating in Saffron: “In 2007, I wanted to avoid arrest and ran away because I knew that staying in prison is not good. I already spent six-seven years in prison since 1988” (Interview 96). A former student activist of the U Thant affair in 1974 also expresses reluctance to get involved in Four-eight: “We were still waiting. Because I was arrested once before so I had experience. So I was watching how to participate so that I would not get arrested” (Interview 149).

Second, ordinary citizens' protection also served to encourage and inspire these dissidents to stage further protests. For example, I find that whether student activists continued their high-risk operations in the aftermath of Four-eight depended on their sense of public support. Whenever they recount their experiences, each mentions how the public came out to cheer, to donate, to protect, or to rescue them. According to a former student activist:

After 1988 when the government crushed the movement, people were afraid and did not dare to participate in demonstrations. But wherever students demonstrated, people went there and clapped. They supported the students. In some places, they gave us money, snacks, water, and towel. (Interview 18)

Such continuous bystander support was a crucial stamp of validation for the Burmese pro-democracy activists and encouraged them to carry on.

During Saffron, Ashin Htavara (2015) also emphasizes the public's warm and enthusiastic support and patronage as a main motivation for the monks to start protesting and marching on September 17, 2007. Later, he refers repeatedly to the group donations, human chains, and collective rescue throughout his experience during Saffron to show the impressive extent of public support and solidarity with the movement and express his pride in the movement. For example, on September 26, while he and other movement participants were beaten due to chanting *Metta Sutta* and marching to Sule pagoda, as many bystanders then immediately joined the human chains to protect the monks, this became an unforgettable moment of public unity that inspired the movement organizers to move forward (Ashin Htavara, 2015). Thus, despite repeated bouts of government crackdown during the final days of Four-eight and Saffron, public support was constantly deemed a very important factor that inspired protest leaders to try again to stage new protests. Overall, bystander protection not only helped a large number of opposition members survive, but also prolonged their dedication to high-risk dissident cause, hence, significantly limiting the effectiveness of state repression.

CONCLUSION

By taking into account the under-analyzed role of civilian bystanders, this study offers a new framework to comprehend opportunities and constraints around movement entrepreneurs in hostile environments. Particularly, based on my analysis of qualitative interviews and primary written accounts on urban pro-democracy movement under Myanmar's military dictatorships, I demonstrate that a type of non-contentious action by civilians, namely high-risk protection, affects activist survival and long-term participation by moderating the efficiency of authoritarian repression and reinforcing activists' pride and sense of public validation for their work. Ultimately, the continued involvement of these activists contributed to the pro-democracy movement's resilience.

This study makes three main contributions. First, by showcasing diverse voices of civilians from various demographic and political backgrounds, my research opens the black box of civilian actions and reactions during major episodes of dissident activism under dictatorship. I demonstrate that ordinary citizens respond in myriad different ways when they encounter contentious mobilizations. Particularly, despite political withdrawal, average bystanders' exposure to protester images as innocent sufferers of excessive violence not only built tolerance toward protesters but also motivation to provide high-risk protective support. Although such acts have gone under-documented and under-analyzed in the social movement literature, they have far-reaching effects on the very dynamics and outcomes of repressed contentious movements.

Indeed, by performing rigorous qualitative analysis on two hard cases for activist resilience against violent repression, this paper makes a second contribution in systematically demonstrating mechanisms through which various forms of bystander protection enable protesters' survival and long-term participation. As evidence from the Myanmar case elucidates, local residents, neighborhoods, monasteries, and mosques were quite dedicated in their attempts to save protest leaders and participants. People informed activists of spies and security forces who were looking for them. They also formed human shields around protesters. In some cases, local residents witnessing protesters being hurt even threw rocks and attacked the perpetrators, who were in fact riot police. When protesters were injured while running away from riot police or soldiers, people either treated the injured at home or sent them to the hospital. They helped opposition members to hide, get a place to sleep, get new clothes and disguises to pass government checkpoints, and escape. Hence, average bystanders' high-risk protection contributed to saving dissidents' lives, leading to politically meaningful outcomes.

Last but not least, I make a third contribution in particular toward the social movement literature by providing an additional framework of non-state agents moderating the effectiveness of state repression. A number of studies on the Middle East, Africa, and Latin America have highlighted the ability of protest participants to win the support by security forces (riot police, military, etc.) as the most crucial factor leading to movement success (Bellin, 2012; Chenoweth et al., 2017; DeMeritt, 2016; Koren, 2014). My research complements these studies by demonstrating that, even in cases where the majority of the security forces did not defect, the capacity by average citizens alone to protect dissidents and refuse cooperation with the authorities had an indirect impact on movement resilience in hostile environments.

To further our understanding on contentious dynamics under repression, I suggest that future research investigates (1) major factors that shape bystanders' perception of dissidents as victims and (2) evolution of bystander protection in today's digitally integrated societies. Despite having popular demands and employing a non-violent method, contentious movements nowadays are increasingly vulnerable to their governments' offline and online disinformation campaigns to vilify activists as rioters. In Myanmar itself, in response to widespread resistance against the 2021 military coup, the Myanmar military constantly promoted propaganda accusing protesters of engaging in "anarchic mob like activities and sabotage activities", arson, murder, rape, etc. (Lintner, 2021, para. 4; Global Witness, 2021; Nachemson, 2021). In such situations, how might activists portray themselves as non-threatening toward other civilians? Which protester images tend to resonate with average bystanders' victim frame? Relatedly, what affordances might new digital technologies provide for dissidents and sympathetic bystanders to connect and coordinate? In the wake of the 2021 coup, neighborhoods across Myanmar, for instance, have been known to form groups on various social media platforms to inform anti-coup activists of troop movements (Jordt

et al., 2021). Overall, addressing these pressing questions will allow us to develop a more precise theoretical framework of contentious dynamics in modern-day authoritarianism.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I thank the Yangon School of Political Science and many other individuals, as well as independent libraries, museums, bookstores, and institutions in Yangon, Myanmar for their generous support and guidance during my data collection and analysis process. I also benefited from comments and feedback by the two anonymous reviewers, Tom Pepinsky, Matthew Evangelista, Jeremy Wallace, Nic van de Walle, Sid Tarrow, Tyrell Haberkorn, Kai Ostwald, Maria Thaemar C. Tana, and participants at University of Essex–University of the Philippines Diliman's Beyond Essentialism Workshop, Cornell University's Southeast Asia Program Lecture Series, the Association for Asian Studies Conference, and the Nordic Institute of Asian Studies' Lunch Talk Series. The author received funding from Cornell University for the field research. The work on this article was also supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 101079069).

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ENDNOTES

¹ During late 1988–early 1989, General Saw Maung's military brutally cracked down on the Four-eight Uprising, causing thousands of deaths and thousands more arrests. Then, in 1990, as the main opposition party, NLD, won a landslide in the May 1990 general election, the ruling junta dismissed the results and started to arrest hundreds of opposition party members and activists. Hundreds of student activists were also detained after they held a pro-democracy demonstration in December 1991 in celebration of Aung San Suu Kyi's 1991 Nobel Peace Prize. As a result, the number of political prisoners exploded to around 2000 in early 1992. Later on, in May 1996, the Burmese junta continued to crack down on hundreds of NLD activists in May when the party announced to draft a separate Constitution. Then, after 1998, when thousands of students protested and, along with NLD members, advocated Aung San Suu Kyi's call for the convening of a parliament, the military regime again ratcheted up its arrest campaign between 1999 and 2001. This resulted in a total of more than 1800 activists imprisoned in 2001. See reports by Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, and UN Special Rapporteurs of the Commission on Human Rights.

² The Burmese Buddhist script of loving kindness.

³ The Village Act and The Towns Act, adopted under British colonial rule and remained effective until 2012, required Myanmar residents to report about overnight houseguests to local authorities. Failure to register guests is punished with fines and imprisonment. The military regimes have been known to employ these laws to arrest dissidents in hiding at night. See Christina Fink's *Living silence in Burma* and Fortify Rights' 2015 publication *Midnight intrusions*.

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How to cite this article: Tran, MV. (2023). Enabling activist resilience: Bystander protection during protest crackdowns in Myanmar. *Asian Politics and Policy*, 15(2), 205–225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aspp.12683>

APPENDIX A

FIGURE A My interview sample's demographics and protest engagement.